

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Future primary school teachers must possess didactic abilities in many respects. In particular, preparing visual aids for working with children of primary school age, applying electronic educational technologies in lessons, and presenting them in a “language” that children can understand are of great importance. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the level of development of students’ information competence. This is because students’ ability to work with information and deliver it to a children’s audience in an audiovisual manner ensures the effectiveness of education. For this reason, identifying the factors that influence the development of students’ information competence and, on this basis, forming the relevant competence in future primary school teachers is of great importance.*

Keywords: *information competence, cognitive, technological, motivational-value-based, creative, visual aids, electronic educational technologies.*

Introduction

Today, one of the requirements placed on modern specialists is their information competence. Information competence occupies an important place in the professional formation of students in the field of primary education. A student’s information competence is an integral characteristic that includes knowledge of information and communication technologies and the ability to use them in creative activity. Students’ information competence also facilitates their professional adaptation.

In theoretical sources, this competence includes the following components: cognitive, technological, motivational-value-based, and creative. Let us consider each component:

The cognitive component is based on knowledge related to information and information technologies. It includes knowledge about information and communication technologies that can be used in professional activity, as well as knowledge and skills related to intellectual activity.

The technological component includes skills in working with information sources and large volumes of data, mastering methods of processing them, cooperating in the information space, and searching for, analyzing, collecting, and presenting information from the virtual world.

The motivational-value-based component refers to the student’s value-based attitude toward information technologies. It includes the student’s self-development and creative approach to the informatization of education.

The creative component includes creative understanding of information and proposing new ideas in the information space.

Materials and Methods

Taking into account the importance of the development of information competence in future primary school teachers, we organized diagnostic work. For this purpose, we administered the questionnaire “Determination of Social-Information Competence,” developed by N. A.

Stepanova, L. N. Sannikova, S. N. Yurevich, and N. I. Levshina, to 374 respondents selected for the study.

In the study, in order to analyze the dynamics of the development of information competence, we analyzed the results obtained by year of study. The results are presented in the following table.

Table 2.7. Dynamic Characteristics of Students' Information Competence $n = 374$

Indicators	1st year N	1st year Mean rank	2nd year N	2nd year Mean rank	3rd year N	3rd year Mean rank	4th year N	4th year Mean rank	H	p
Cognitive	92	141.68	95	166.30	97	217.74	90	224.12	40.281**	0.000
Technological	92	192.52	95	162.02	97	201.15	90	194.56	7.568	0.056
Motivational- value-based	92	206.40	95	173.55	97	188.53	90	181.79	5.163	0.160

Note: * $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$

Results and Discussion

The results obtained from our dissertation research were analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis criterion H. According to the results, statistically significant differences were found only in the cognitive component of students' indicators: $H = 40.281$; $p \leq 0.01$.

If we analyze the students' results, we can observe that the cognitive component of information competence changed from the first year to the fourth year. This situation shows that, among students in the field of primary education, the increase in knowledge about information technologies, the virtual world, and its possibilities, as well as the formation of skills for working with digitized information, led to an increase in the manifestation of their cognitive processes.

The cognitive component of social-information competence includes the independent acquisition of knowledge related to information and information objects. The level of the cognitive component in students is determined by the completeness, depth, and systematic nature of their knowledge related to the field of study. If we look at the results of our students, we can see that the more thoroughly the foundations of the subject are mastered, the more their cognitive sphere expands.

As students in the field of primary education master specialized subjects, their level of literacy related to information technologies increases. This contributed to the increase in information competence among fourth-year students compared with students admitted to the first year. In addition, the growth of the cognitive component of students' information competence across years of study is also connected with an increase in skills for receiving, using, and managing information.

In particular, the teaching of general subject modules in the first year contributes to the formation of students' skills in receiving, selecting, and processing information, while the increase in specialized subjects in the third and fourth years strengthens the process of synthesizing knowledge related to information technologies with professional activity.

As a result, students in the field of primary education try to connect their professional knowledge with digital technologies through continuity and consistency in practice.

This creates opportunities to apply knowledge related to information technologies within the framework of the specialty. Therefore, significant differences were observed in the results between years of study.

No significant differences were found in the technological component of information competence among future primary school teachers. If we pay attention to the results, we can see that the indicators for this criterion have uneven development. For example, the lowest value was observed in the second year. This indicates unevenness in development. However, the differences between the years of study are not statistically significant.

Similarly, no significant difference was observed in the motivational-value-based component. However, if we look at the results, the indicators decreased from the first year to the fourth year. This means that students' perception of information as a value decreased by the fourth year.

In general, students' information competence leads to the development of a critical attitude toward social information, the spread of information in the mass media, the ability to orient themselves in the information flow, checking the reliability of information, and strengthening a creative approach. This is connected with the growth of students' professional knowledge and the formation of their practical skills.

According to the analysis of the above empirical data, it was determined that the following aspects are important in the information competence of future primary school teachers. In particular, the ability to work with social information leads to the strengthening of cognitive processes:

The development of students' visual, auditory, and tactile sensations through working with information technologies;

The strengthening of perception connected with the use of digital technologies in education, the extraction of information, and the intensification of effects in working with information;

The strengthening of processes connected with storing information, the breadth of the world of imagination in working with information, and focusing attention on educational information;

The development of creative thinking and inner speech in the processing of digitized information was observed.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the priority of the cognitive component was identified in the level of development of information competence among future primary school teachers.

At the next stage of our dissertation research, we studied the dependence of the dynamics of students' information competence development on learning motives. This is because, according to our assumption, students' information competence develops in connection with the educational process and educational motives. Therefore, the relationship between the results obtained from the questionnaire "Determination of Social-Information Competence," developed by N. A. Stepanova, L. N. Sannikova, S. N. Yurevich, and N. I. Levshina, and the results of the questionnaire "Diagnostics of Students' Learning Motivation," modified by A. A. Rean, V. A. Yakunin, and N. S. Badmayeva, was studied.

Initially, we considered it appropriate to analyze students' learning motivation more deeply. The main reason for this is that the development of learning motives in students and their manifestation in activity is a complex process. Educational activity combines many qualities and

skills of the student's personality; they determine the structure of the student's personality, their scientific and creative potential, and the individual style of educational activity.

Table 2.8. Dynamic Characteristics of Students' Learning Motives $n = 374$

Indicators	1st year N	1st year Mean rank	2nd year N	2nd year Mean rank	3rd year N	3rd year Mean rank	4th year N	4th year Mean rank	H	p
Communicative motives	92	208.68	95	182.67	97	192.62	90	165.43	7.766	0.051
Avoidance motive	92	236.18	95	167.20	97	188.38	90	158.22	29.083**	0.000
Prestige motives	92	214.93	95	189.56	97	185.79	90	159.12	12.416**	0.006
Professional motives	92	217.02	95	173.19	97	193.02	90	166.49	12.276**	0.006
Motives for realizing one's abilities in the field of creativity	92	220.60	95	174.56	97	196.38	90	157.76	18.144**	0.000
Learning and cognitive motives	92	205.67	95	197.14	97	188.08	90	158.12	10.120*	0.018
Social motives	92	176.26	95	201.31	97	193.09	90	178.39	3.511	0.319

Note: * $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$

To study students' motivational sphere, especially to examine learning motivation more deeply, we analyzed the results obtained from the questionnaire "Diagnostics of Students' Learning Motivation," modified by A. A. Rean, V. A. Yakunin, and N. S. Badmayeva, by years of study. After analyzing the results by year of study, we examined their relationship with information competence. The results obtained from these methods are presented in Table 2.8.

The results obtained from our dissertation research were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis criterion H. According to the results, statistically significant differences were identified in students' indicators for avoidance motives ($H = 29.083$; $p \leq 0.01$), prestige motives ($H = 12.416$; $p \leq 0.01$), professional motives ($H = 12.276$; $p \leq 0.01$), motives for realizing one's abilities in the field of creativity ($H = 18.144$; $p \leq 0.01$), and learning and cognitive motives ($H = 10.120$; $p \leq 0.05$). The interesting aspect of our results is that all motives decreased from the first year to the fourth year. Although a decrease in avoidance is natural, in our opinion, the results for the other motives should have increased.

The next type of students' learning motives is avoidance motives. Avoidance is also more dominant among first-year students. This situation is connected with students' motive to avoid failure. Among first-year students, this consists of fear of failure in completing tasks and fear of being unable to overcome difficulties in acquiring professional knowledge. Usually, first-year students are afraid of encountering difficulties in completing pedagogical tasks because they lack the relevant competencies.

As a result, didactogenic fears and education-related anxieties arise among students. This causes them to search for "easy ways" when completing complex tasks and strengthens their

motives of “avoidance.” In addition, after being admitted as students, under the influence of the “adaptation syndrome” connected with adjustment to the educational process, the student tries to act in accordance with the social expectations of teachers. As a result, in order not to encounter various organizational and social problems, the student demonstrates adaptive behavior, and the corresponding motives are activated. By the fourth year, these motives naturally decrease due to adaptation to the educational environment. Therefore, these motives decreased from year to year, and significant differences were observed in this case.

The next motive in the dissertation is the prestige motive, and higher results for this motive were also found among first-year students. This situation is connected with students’ attempts to find their social position in the group. As a student admitted to the first year strives to strengthen their position in the group and adapt, they try to ensure that their self is valued. This leads to the intensive manifestation of their motives for prestige. As students move from year to year and acquire their own position in the group, the level of manifestation of the motive for striving for prestige decreases somewhat. This decrease led to the emergence of statistically significant differences.

Conclusion

Based on the above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The development of information competence in students has a dynamic character, and it was found that the cognitive component intensifies with the formation of students’ professional knowledge.
2. As a result of the influence of learning motives on the development of information competence among future primary school teachers, it was observed that “professional” and “learning-cognitive” motives have a priority character, because students’ focus of attention on educational information and the expansion of their world of imagination in working with didactic information are more strongly manifested under the influence of the cognitive component.

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